

Notes

Synthetic and Antimicrobial Studies of some Heterocyclic Hydrazones and their Bivalent Metal Complexes

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The interest in the study of hydrazones possessing potential donor sites has been intensively increasing owing to their coordinating capability¹, their pharmacological activity² and their uses in analytical chemistry as metal extracting agents³. It has also been reported that the activity of biometals is very often altered through the formation of complexes with different bioligands, and furthermore the biological activity of an active molecule is altered quantitatively on coordinating with a suitable metal ion⁴. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to synthesise some hydrazones by the condensation of the dihydrazides of iminodiacetic acid/pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid with 2-acetylfuran and their Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with a view to see the combined activity of the metal and the ligands.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were found coloured and stable at room temperature. Their solubility varied in different common organic solvents. Their low molar conductance values (2.55–5.67 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) were in good agreement to their non-electrolytic nature. Analytical data (Table 1) of the metal complexes were found consistent with their 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometry.

Ir spectral studies : Ir spectra of both the free ligands exhibited some common bands at 3 140 (NH), 1 650 (C=C amide I), 1 605 (C=N) and 1 030 cm⁻¹ (N-N). In addition, the pyridine ring deformation bands, in the ir spectra of AFPDH, at 410 (out-of-plane) and 620 cm⁻¹ (in-plane) were also observed. Both the ligands functioned as tetradentate ligands coordinating through amide oxygen and azomethine N as evident by downward displacement of $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ bands by 40–50 and 10–15 cm⁻¹ respectively in the complexes. The band due to ν_{NH} remained almost unaltered in the spectra of the respective complexes ruling out the involvement of this group in complexation. Furthermore, the coordination from one of the nitrogen atoms of N-N bond is indicated by a small shift of ν_{N-N} bond to higher wave-number ($\sim 1 045$ cm⁻¹) as compared to its position in the ligand⁶. Ir spectra of all the metal complexes showed two bands at 1 625 and 1 355 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{as} and ν_s modes of the coordinated acetate group. Monodentate coordination of the acetate group results in the ν_{as} mode appearing at higher energy and the ν_s at lower energy compared to ν_{as} and ν_s modes of the uncoordinated acetate group (1 580 and 1 425 cm⁻¹)⁶. Since the pyridine ring deformation vibrations do not experience any

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF HYDRAZONES AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p./Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	Metal
1.	AFIH(L)	Light brown	197–98	52.49 (52.99)	5.03 (4.73)	22.54 (22.08)	—
2.	Cu(L)(OAc) ₂	Blue	253	43.02 (43.32)	4.07 (4.21)	14.22 (14.04)	13.54 (12.74)
3.	Ni(L)(OAc) ₂	Green	278	44.13 (43.75)	4.42 (4.25)	14.34 (14.17)	11.33 (11.88)
4.	Co(L)(OAc) ₂	Dark brown	248	43.51 (43.73)	4.39 (4.25)	13.89 (14.17)	12.56 (11.88)
5.	AFPDH(L')	Brownish white	166–68	61.17 (61.91)	5.20 (5.15)	17.26 (17.19)	—
6.	Cu(L')(OAc) ₂	Blue	289	50.60 (50.97)	4.23 (4.58)	12.03 (11.80)	10.45 (10.79)
7.	Ni(L')(OAc) ₂	Green	307	51.74 (51.39)	4.38 (4.62)	11.64 (11.99)	11.15 (10.05)
8.	Co(L')(OAc) ₂	Light pink	281	51.65 (51.37)	4.82 (4.62)	12.19 (11.99)	10.97 (10.05)

TABLE 2—LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF METAL COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	10 Dq cm^{-1}	B	β	L.F.S.E. kcal mol^{-1}	ν_2/ν_1	Dq/B
1.	Cu(L)(OAc) ₂	15540	—	—	26.64	—	—
2.	Ni(L)(OAc) ₂	9500	808.3	0.78	32.57	1.65	1.17
3.	Co(L)(OAc) ₂	8300	858.3	0.88	14.23	2.11	0.96
4.	Cu(L')(OAc) ₂	18125	—	+	31.07	—	—
5.	Ni(L')(OAc) ₂	10800	711.6	0.68	37.02	1.66	1.51
6.	Co(L')(OAc) ₂	8105	811.0	0.83	13.89	2.01	0.99

*L=AFIH; L'=AFPDH.

positive or negative shift, the non-involvement of pyridinyl-N in complexation is inferred. The non-ligand bands at 470–485 and 380–400 cm^{-1} support the formation of M–N and M–O bonds respectively⁷, which further confirm the above assignments.

Electronic spectra and magnetic studies: The μ_{eff} value for the Co^{II} complexes are 4.82 and 4.98 B.M., suggesting thereby a high-spin octahedral geometry for these complexes⁸, which is further supported by their electronic spectral data. The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes showed three bands at 7 500–8 050, 15 800–16 155 and 19 575–20 160 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. The ratio ν_2/ν_1 (2.11 and 2.01) agrees well with the reported values for octahedral Co^{II} complexes⁹.

Electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes displayed $d-d$ bands at 9 500–10 800, 15 675–17 925 and 24 950–25 150 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The 23% reduction in B value as compared to free Ni^{II} ion (1 040 cm^{-1}) indicates its complexation. Lowering of the ratio ν_2/ν_1 from 1.8 (theoretical value) to 1.65 and 1.66 due to configuration interaction between $T_{1g}(P)$ and $T_{1g}(F)$ excited states is in conformity with the distorted octahedral geometry¹⁰ of both the complexes which is further supported by their μ_{eff} values (3.07 and 3.12 B.M.).

A broad band at 15 540–18 125 cm^{-1} and another at 28 221–30 670 cm^{-1} are observed in the spectrum of the Cu^{II} complexes. The former band may be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transitions, suggesting thereby a distorted octahedral geometry for these complexes¹¹. The latter band can be attributed to L→M charge transfer band. The Cu^{II} complexes exhibited normal magnetic moments (1.85 and 1.92 B.M.) observed for d^9 system with one unpaired electron. This accounts for a slight orbital contribution to the spin-only value and absence of spin-spin interactions in the complexes⁸.

Different ligand field parameters (viz. L.F.S.E., 10 Dq , B , β and ν_2/ν_1) (Table 2) for all the metal complexes have been calculated from their electronic spectral data, which are in good agreement with the geometry proposed to them.

Antimicrobial activity: The in vitro antimicrobial screening of both the ligands and their respec-

tive metal complexes against two bacteria, viz. *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli* (gram-negative) (incubation period, 24 h at 37°) and two fungi, viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* (incubation period, 96 h at 28°), was carried out following the serial dilution method¹². Test solutions of AFIH and AFPDH were prepared in propylene glycol and those of the complexes in DMSO diluted with culture media to give the required drug concentration in 2.5% DMSO. Comparison of MIC values (Table 3) of AFIH, AFPDH and their metal complexes reveal an increase in the antimicrobial activity of ligands in the form of their metal complexes. Ligand AFIH was biologically more active than AFPDH against the test organisms used. In terms of metal complexes the order of antibacterial activity was found as Cu>Ni≈Co. The order of antifungal activity

TABLE 3—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY (MIC VALUES $\mu\text{g/ml}^{-1}$)* OF HYDRAZONES AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	S.a	E.c	A.n	C.a
AFIH(L)	50	50	75	75
Cu(L)(OAc) ₂	6.25	12.50	6.25	12.50
Ni(L)(OAc) ₂	12.50	6.25	12.50	12.50
Co(L)(OAc) ₂	12.50	12.50	12.50	12.50
AFPDH(L')	75	7	100.0	100
Cu(L')(OAc) ₂	3.125	3.125	3.125	6.25
Ni(L')(OAc) ₂	6.25	6.25	3.125	12.50
Co(L')(OAc) ₂	6.25	6.25	12.50	3.125

*S.a≡*S. aureus*; E.c≡*E. coli*; A.n≡*A. niger*; C.a≡*C. albicans*

in terms of metal complexes of AFIH against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* was Cu>Ni≈Co and Cu≈Ni≈Co, respectively, and that of the metal complexes of AFPDH against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* was Cu≈Ni>Co and Co>Cu>Ni respectively. From these observations, it is clear that in all cases (except Co^{II} complexes of AFPDH against *C. albicans*), Cu^{II} complexes were more active than the others which is due to the faster diffusion of the Cu^{II} complexes through cell membrane than the Ni^{II}/Cu^{II} complexes on account of more liposolubility of the former complexes.

Moreover, the faster diffusion of Cu^{II} complexes may probably be due to the following reasons: (i) among the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} metal ions, the smallest ionic radius of Cu^{II} ion facilitates the faster diffusion in comparison to rest of the ions,

and (ii) since copper forms more stable complexes than nickel and cobalt which are insoluble in water. Hence, solubility of copper complexes in lipid causes comparatively faster diffusion.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Iminodiacetic acid dihydrazide and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid dihydrazide were synthesised from their corresponding dimethyl esters of acids and hydrazine hydrate by the reported procedure¹³.

Hydrazones: 2-Acetylfuran-*N*-iminodiacetyl hydrazone (AFIH) and 2-acetylfuran-*N*-pyridine-2,6-dicarboxyloyl hydrazone (AFPDH) were synthesised by condensing 2 : 1 molar amounts of 2-acetylfuran with iminodiacetic acid dihydrazide or pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid dihydrazide. On concentrating the resulting solution to one-third of its original volume under reduced pressure and keeping it overnight in refrigerator, coloured crystals were separated which were washed with cold ethanol (0°) and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂. Their purity was checked by tlc method.

Metal complexes: Hot ethanolic solutions of ligand (0.01 mol) and metal acetate (0.01 mol) were mixed in stoichiometric ratio with continuous stirring. The resulting solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. On concentrating and cooling, the resulting coloured solids were washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂.

The purity of the hydrazones and their metal complexes were judged by their C, H and N analyses. Metal contents were estimated by standard procedures¹⁴. Ir spectra (KBr/polyethylene disc) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer

and electronic spectra (DMSO) on a Shimadzu UV-150-02 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance was measured in dry DMSO using a Toshniwal conductivity meter at room temperature. Gouy's method was employed for magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temperature using CuSO₄. 5H₂O as the calibrant.

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